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Calcium, Barium, Copper or Zinc Hydroxylapatites Solid Solutions. Preparation and Lattice Constant Measurements

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HYDROXYLAPATITE $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, (CaHA) is recognised as the most important of the inorganic constituents of human bone and teeth¹. It belongs to an isomorphous series of compounds known as apatite which undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions². Replacement of Ca^{II} by Ba^{II} and/or Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} ions in CaHA are of extreme biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Ba^{II} and Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} ions into human skeletal system according to

where, $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{II}$ or Zn^{II} . The present paper describes the results of X-ray diffraction studies on some synthetic Ca | Ba | Cu | Zn hydroxylapatites.

Experimental

Solid solutions of calcium, barium and copper or zinc hydroxylapatites were prepared separately earlier³ by firing mixture containing various proportions of calcium, barium and copper or zinc hydroxylapatites at about 1300°. These samples prepared by solid state reaction were, however, found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous. An attempt was made using a new method of preparation of homogeneous solid solutions of mixed (Ca+Ba+Cu or Zn) hydroxylapatites over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation⁴.

where, $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{II}$ or Zn^{II} ; when, $n=1$, $(l+m)=9$ for one series and when, $l=1$, $(m+n)=9$ for the other series.

Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} and Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} ions in the proportion

desired for the solid solutions (solution B) were prepared separately in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. At pH 11, solutions A and B were taken separately and added dropwise to the content (a few ml of solution B) simultaneously. The precipitate and mother liquor were aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate, and the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate, since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of calcium-deficient apatites⁵. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with double-distilled water to free it from ammonium salts. Samples dried at 100° for few hours were analysed complexometrically and their molar volumes determined by density method using toluene⁶ as a solvent.

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were obtained with a Siemens powder diffractometer with NaCl (TL) counter employing $\text{Cu}-\text{K}\alpha$ (Ni-filtered) radiation, with a scanning speed of 1° (2 θ) per min (using tube voltage of 30 kV, and 24 mA). The results of chemical analysis, *d*-spacing and the corresponding *a* and *c* parameters calculated by the method of Azaroff⁷, and the unit cell volumes of the samples are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total 10 g atoms of Ca and/or Ba and/or Cu or Zn, the molecular formula of the samples were calculated from the results of columns 3–5 and included in column 2 of Table 1. The g-atom ratios (Ca+Ba+Cu or Zn)/P in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of columns 3–6 and given in column 7 of Table 1. The fact that the observed values of molar g-atom ratios of Ca/P, Ba/P, Cu/P, Zn/P, for the end-members and (Ca+Ba+Cu or Zn)/P found to be equal to 1.666 (theoretical value 1.67), are consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁸. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end-members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end-members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal symmetry belonging to hexagonal bipyramidal class, $^63/m$ (space group $\text{P}_{63/m}$)⁹. Lattice parameters showed unit cell dilation consequent upon the introduction of bigger

TABLE I—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF MIXED SOLID SOLUTIONS OF Ca, Ba, Cu or Zn AND MEASUREMENT OF LATTICE PARAMETERS

Formulation	Wt %				g-atom ratio (Ca+Ba+Cu/Zn)/P	Lattice parameters		Unit cell volume $\sqrt{3}/2 a^3$
	Ca	Ba	Cu/Zn	P		a	c	
Ca _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	39.89	—	—	18.50	1.666	9.37	6.86	523.12
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.10} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.35	60.10	3.90	10.36	1.667	9.87	7.29	615.02
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.37	55.17	7.50	10.76	1.667	—	—	—
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.51	49.89	11.22	11.20	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.95} Ba _{0.07} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.40	48.10	16.37	11.74	1.666	9.55	7.12	562.86
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.04} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.69	35.92	21.90	12.34	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.07} Cu _{1.01} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.89	27.62	27.16	13.03	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{1.04} Ba _{0.11} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	3.07	19.85	33.04	13.71	1.666	9.16	6.71	487.52
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.15} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	3.30	8.63	40.66	14.59	1.667	—	—	—
Ca _{1.05} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	3.33	—	46.99	15.29	1.667	8.92	6.55	451.34
Cu _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	—	—	51.27	14.99	1.667	8.88	6.58	440.93
Ca _{0.9} Ba _{1.1} Zn _{0.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	23.26	13.31	5.19	16.98	1.667	9.42	6.91	581.02
Ca _{0.71} Ba _{1.05} Zn _{0.95} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	23.35	21.98	5.10	15.26	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.65} Ba _{0.95} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	18.76	29.84	5.20	14.22	1.666	9.49	6.96	542.84
Ca _{0.65} Ba _{0.95} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	14.33	38.11	4.72	13.16	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.61} Ba _{1.05} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	10.63	44.95	4.50	12.29	1.667	9.81	7.07	589.23
Ca _{0.55} Ba _{1.05} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	7.32	51.03	4.25	11.51	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.55} Ba _{0.95} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	4.74	56.04	3.86	10.88	1.666	9.99	7.19	621.43
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Zn _{0.95} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.33	60.81	3.44	10.29	1.667	—	—	—
Ba _{0.95} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	—	64.78	3.50	9.76	1.667	10.05	7.45	651.66
Ba _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	—	69.46	—	9.41	1.665	10.19	7.70	692.42

ion Ba^{II} (1.35 Å) and contraction upon the introduction of smaller ion Cu^{II} (0.72 Å) or Zn^{II} (0.74 Å) in place of Ca^{II} ion (0.99 Å) in the apatite lattice. Such contraction of Ca–Ba–CuHA was also evident from the fact that the unit cell volume of the samples (calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constants) decreased with the decrease in the proportion of barium content and consequent increase in the proportion of copper content in Ca–Ba–CuHA. Such dilation of (Ca+Ba+Zn)HA was evident from excellent regularity with which the unit cell volume of the samples increased with increase in the proportion of barium content keeping zinc constant in the mixed solid solutions.

All compositions of solid solution formation were confirmed from the fact that X-ray diffraction findings revealed no reflections except those pertaining to the mixed crystals.

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Chromium(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with 3-(*m*-Nitrobenzylideneamino)-2-methyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolone

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THE present paper reports the result of our studies on the synthesis and characterisation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cr^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with the Schiff base derived from 2-methyl-3-amino-4(3*H*)-quinazolone and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of Schiff base: A mixture of 2-methyl-3-amino-4(3*H*)-quinazolone¹ and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol along with a few drops of triethylamine (as catalyst) was refluxed for 4 h. 3-(*m*-Nitrobenzylideneamino)-2-methyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolone precipitated as